

I KNOW THAT YOU KNOW HOW I FEEL: EMOTIONAL ATTUNEMENT OF GUIDANCE COUNSELORS IN PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOLS

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I Know That You Know How I Feel: Emotional Attunement of Guidance Counselors in Public High Schools

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Abstract

This qualitative multiple-case study examines the emotional attunement of guidance counselors in public schools, specifically within General Santos City. Data were collected from four (4) guidance counselors working at different public high schools. This study used a purposive sampling design that explored the challenges, coping mechanisms, and lessons acquired in their field. Based on the gathered data, the views of the guidance counselors had the following emergent themes: offering spiritual counseling, being people-oriented, blessing others, taking responsibility, being able to listen to others' advice, having negative experiences present, showing fair treatment, and concentration is better. Meanwhile, the challenges were feeling drained, lack of cooperation and support, children's lack of tender attention, experiencing the same scenario with parents, and getting irritated. In contrast, the coping mechanisms were having "me time," handling a matter calmly, spreading awareness, engaging in social activities, seeking help from God, building collaboration, scheduling another session, and learning to accept things. Moreover, their insights were that dedication to the profession is necessary, being surrounded by positive people, appreciating the work of a guidance counselor, looking for inspiration to go on, following the right thing, and improving more. Cross-case analysis revealed similarities and differences in themes executed by all guidance counselors, but all performed well in providing guidance and counseling.

Keywords: *guidance and counseling, guidance counselors, emotional attunement, counseling, multiple case study, philippines*

Introduction

This paper describes the emotional attunement of guidance counselors in public high schools, their means of coping with the challenges they faced while providing guidance and counseling services, and lessons learned that they could share with other guidance counselors and the academe. This is directed toward a greater understanding of the value of using emotional attunement as guidance counselors to assist clients in raising their energy levels, reconnecting with their true inner selves, and harmonizing their abilities, interests, and values to reach their full potential.

The Act of 2004 which is called the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004 (Republic Act 9258) and the "Philippine Psychology Act of 2009" (Republic Act 10029) both recognize the significance of these experts in nation-building and ensure that the public receives services from qualified professionals. Therapists and counselors played a supporting role in the recovery from mental illness. They are seasoned and well-trained professionals who protect clients and promise them. However, doing so does not protect their psychological health from the damaging effects of being exposed to their clients' repeated narratives of trauma or pain (Florentino, 2020; Ladd, 2018).

This study intends to share their experiences to encourage and increase awareness of the significant function of emotional attunement in one's life. Such knowledge enabled appropriate responses to any emergent event they were confronted with.

Literature Review

2.1 Emotional Attunement of Guidance Counselor

The school counselor's role has evolved over the last several decades from providing guidance services to one that now administers comprehensive school counseling programs targeting academic, career, and social/emotional development. Counseling, consulting, curriculum, and coordination are reasonable employment duties. These responsibilities include providing individual and small group counseling to students, consulting with stakeholders, facilitating school-wide crisis management responses, conducting classroom lessons, analyzing disaggregated data, designing interventions, and facilitating school-wide crisis management responses (Havlik et al., 2019; Randick et al., 2018; Roffers, 2021; Sinesiou & Henderson, 2020).

The concept of attunement in mentoring relationships is characterized as the ability to adapt one's response to verbal and nonverbal cues while taking into account the wants and preferences of others. Attunement represents a broad strategy to elicit, read, interpret, and reflect on youth cues and requires adaptation of expectations based on others' interests. Finally, attunement involves a level of intentionality in building the relationship. Experiences of attunement, a deeply felt and embodied state of consciousness that results from tuning in to oneself, others, events, energies, and the environment, are the basis for the realization of innate human capacities for connection and growth (Pryce et al., 2018; Snead, 2018).

Emotional Attunement Definition

Attunement is a crucial idea of human development and the foundation of fulfilling relationships. It is the process of understanding and responding to another's spoken and unspoken needs. A common term used to explain and comprehend the process of nonverbal communication is attunement. Attunement is a fundamental concept in developmental psychology that describes the interaction between an infant and a caregiver. It also depicts nonverbal communication and interactions between two or more people. According to Siegel (2013), presence is openness to unlimited possibilities, and attunement is how we focus on others and take their essence into our inner world. According to this definition, attunement includes self-awareness, other awareness, and the present-moment awareness and clear perception required to connect with others (Andreason, 2019; Jacobsen et al., 2021; Kroier et al., 2022).

Process of Attunement

Attunement in the context of psychotherapy is a procedure through which therapists assist patients in symbolizing and making meaning of their interior states. The therapists may attune to their patients when they offer conjectures about what the patient may feel or when they validate the patient's internal experience. This process mirrors or is contained in the psychoanalytic literature. The dynamic interactive processes intrinsic to psychotherapy enable therapists to explore tentatively, imaginatively, and playfully with their patients in a co-constructed conversation. Attunement is intrinsically responsive. As therapists receive their clients' moment-to-moment experiences, they also tune in with themselves to understand what is being received (Geller, 2018; Knox, 2019; Talia et al., 2020).

Significance of Emotional Attunement

Adult psychotherapy relies heavily on attunement. Attunement clarifies how two or more people interact in therapeutic situations while sharing similar internal emotional states. In that it offers a means of seeing the other person's inner world while preserving awareness of one's inner world, attunement is related to empathy. To regulate his mental state and record emotional experiences, thoughts, and images from the counselor and the counselee, the counselor must be fully aware of their internal and external conditions (Andreason, 2019; Hanafi et al., 2022; Kroier et al., 2022).

Personality Competence of Guidance Counselors

The qualities required of a counselor are as follows: having faith and piety in God Almighty; liking people; being an adept communicator and good listener; having knowledge and insight about people; being socio-cultural, flexible, calm, and patient; knowing professional ethics; being respectful, honest, genuine, appreciating, and not passing judgment; being empathetic, understanding, accepting, warm, and friendly; being both a facilitator and a motivator; stable emotions, clear thoughts, fast and capable, objective, rational (Lianasari & Purwati, 2022).

Furthermore, to persuade the client and the counselor alike of the benefits of using religious and spiritual approaches, the focus should be on the counselor's religious, spiritual, and professional competencies. It is imperative to emphasize the client's religious practices and beliefs because they were introduced into the therapeutic environment. One meaningful way to mitigate some of the adverse effects of the religious/spiritual intervention is to establish respect as a fundamental value for the therapeutic dialog and relationship. If religion and spirituality can assist patients in many forms of treatment, they should be included in therapeutic (Frunza et al., 2019).

Listening is one significant skill of guidance counselors. High-quality listening leads to greater satisfaction of both psychological needs. As a result of experiencing such listening, speakers may feel a sense of closeness to the listener (relatedness) and feel they can express their self-congruent views and feelings (autonomy). Their needs for relatedness and autonomy are both satisfied. Therefore, collaboration and communication were essential in providing effective guidance and counseling (Itzchakov et al., 2023; Kruczek et al., 2022).

Guidance counselors emphasize fair treatment for all students, regardless of background or circumstances. A program was established to reduce knowledge gaps, help students reflect on their attitudes, and act as a motivational device for high-achieving students from underprivileged backgrounds. Guidance can also expand students' imaginaries beyond cultural norms, contrasting the role of social norms and values (Borgna et al., 2022; Mursidi & Novindari, 2022).

2.2 Emotional Attunement Challenges of Guidance Counselor

Individuals providing mental health services experience three psychological syndromes of burnout: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. Those who work in the mental health field can develop emotional weariness, depersonalization, and a decreased sense of personal success. School counselors' numerous and more complicated jobs may compromise their welfare, which could affect how well they serve children. It is important to understand burnout because it puts school counselors' ability to provide kids with the required services at risk. School counselors who encounter difficulties at work may get stressed (Chen et al., 2019; Fannon, 2021; Vazquez, 2020).

Delinquency is having a naughty nature, mischievous acts, and mild behavior that violates the norms and laws that apply to society. One of the causes of student delinquency is the estrangement of the bond between parents and their children. It can also occur that acts of juvenile delinquency are anti-social, which cause public unrest in general, but are classified as general criminal offenses and special criminal offenses. There are also anti-moral adolescent actions, namely disobedience to both parents and siblings who are hostile to each other (Andra, 2023). Another challenging reality confronting counselors who want to provide personalized support to their

students is the lack of tender attention to children. Two factors that influenced the characterization of children. First, internal factors, from within the family, where children lack the quality of attention and quality time from parents, and often children get harsh treatment from parents through violence physical as well as verbal violence. Secondly, external factors, from the community environment, where the effect of not going to school is much more significant than positive influence on school. Similarly, the habit of drinking alcoholic beverages and utterance words at least form the character of a child who is not fully strong or in a fragile condition due to a lack of quality attention and quality of time provided by their parents (Emmanuel, 2020; Hermino & Arifin, 2020).

Struggling with similar issues with parents is part of the challenges of guidance counselors. It means they are not exempted from pain and stress while extending help. This can be difficult for counselors who may feel powerless to help the student's family situation. Guidance counselors face both personal and professional challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic. In the helping profession, it was also noteworthy that they value and grounded themselves in selfless service to their clientele. The skills of guidance counselors are coupled with the values they possess to cope with and overcome the challenges they encounter in performing their roles and functions (Pedroso et al., 2022).

2.3 Guidance Counselor Intervention Strategies

One element of Bandura's (1999) social cognitive theory is self-efficacy. It is defined as a counselor's confidence in their ability to conduct counseling quickly and successfully. Self-efficacy is positively correlated with self-control, self-concept, and mastery goal orientation to influence academic performance results from a personal and professional development perspective. The significant career decision and professional choice of an individual are also predicted by self-efficacy belief and linked to significant motivating factors like job satisfaction (Ooi et al., 2018; Parikh-Fox et al., 2020; Tang, 2019).

Additionally, knowing how self-care, perceived stress, and burnout are related might motivate professionals to offer assistance to promote a healthier balance between school counselors' personal and professional lives. Having a general disposition of care and concern for clients is a crucial quality for counselors since counselors can no longer foster wellness in others when they do not have it in themselves. An essential practice that counselors must learn is to turn that care and concern toward themselves, or in other words, have a practice of self-care. Counselors may endure stress in their personal and professional lives if they do not learn to care for themselves, which could result in burnout (Fannon, 2021; Nelson et al., 2018; Randick et al., 2018).

Counselor self-care can be defined as a counselor's actions to teach optimal physical and mental health. Self-care can refer to engaging in activities that promote emotional well-being and alleviate feelings of burnout. Counselors' extended failure to engage in self-care can result in emotional exhaustion, stress, and burnout. Increased self-awareness, self-reflection, and self-care are essential. It is necessary to develop such protective protocols to protect health professionals from being harmed by the work they do (Evans & Ward, 2019).

Calm therapy is a quick, evidence-based, semi-structured intervention that offers a framework to address existential and practical difficulties, such as finding purpose and hope in the face of mortality and navigating the healthcare system and treatment options. It has been demonstrated that CALM helps people with advanced cancer prepare for death and reduces and prevents depression. It is being modified to fit other terminal illnesses, cultural situations, and medical facilities. Advocacy is necessary for people with advanced and life-threatening illnesses to promote such methods (Sethi et al., 2020).

Engaging in social activities, even a simple thing such as meeting friends for a trip to the movies, managing them effectively, and supporting interactions, will be essential to bring peace, calm, and other positive outcomes. Social support plays a crucial role in well-being. Friends and family are integral to each individual's and family's support system. This is the most common coping strategy used to manage stress, and this approach was found to be inversely related to anxiety levels. Seeking out social support is categorized as a problem-focused coping strategy and has been found to effectively reduce stress (Venkatesh, 2020; d'Ettorre et al., 2021).

Seeking social support is an effective coping strategy for counselors to reduce levels of burnout. A supportive environment among school counselors would give mutual understanding throughout the action, as all school counselors would be within the same practicing field (Affandi & Abdullah, 2023).

Moreover, seeking help from God or using religious coping mechanisms such as praying was reported as necessary. The most popular coping strategy and one of the most effective strategies to lessen the mental and psychological load was prayer and other religious practices (Labrague, 2022).

The study also found the importance of seeking and upholding spiritual support and well-being in further persevering through and against burnout. It is reported that those with higher levels of spiritual well-being and daily spiritual experiences were found to possess lower levels of psychological distress and burnout, suggesting it to be a viable protective factor against burnout (Affandi & Abdullah, 2023).

Collaboration is a method of communication and a strategy for delivering services. It is increasingly being seen as a crucial component in addressing students' different learning and behavioral requirements, which has prompted many practitioners to consider its nature and practice. Building collaboration with the student's parents or scheduling another session to address concerns can help resolve conflicts and improve cooperation (Alonso et al., 2018; Montague et al., 2020).

Lastly, they stated that adaptation to life becomes more accessible by learning to accept things and having a positive outlook. Having positive thinking and practicing affirmations are ways counselors cope with burnout. Positivity is one of the concepts addressed in the positive psychology movement. It is a kind of attitude that includes thoughts, words, and images that help growth, development, and success. It also allows individuals to step into the next level of existence, opening their minds and contributing to a promising future. Possessing positive coping skills is a plus, although the action counts most. As a result of taking positive steps, one will find that positive coping skills are automatically enhanced (Agha, 2021; Bakioglu et al., 2021).

The researcher believed that each literature and study stated in this research have similarities to the current research. It comprised topics on the emotional attunement of guidance counselor, their challenges in the counseling field, and their emotional attunement prevention strategies.

The topics previously discussed have shed light on understanding the significance of the construct of emotional attunement in the environment of the client-counselor relationship. Such knowledge creates awareness of how to manage their profession properly. Being attuned to clients and responding appropriately to their needs provides measures and avenues for developing and building trust as a guidance counselor. In this fast-changing world, our youth are directly touched, exercising, and deploying guidance counselor advocacy, which is vital to making counseling in education more attuned to times and the requirements of society.

Methodology

The study used a qualitative research design, particularly a multiple-case study. Qualitative research is multimethod and approaches its subject matter via an interpretive, naturalistic lens. This design investigates phenomena in their natural environments to explain or interpret occurrences in terms of the meanings that individuals assign to them. Its fundamental characteristic explores how individuals interpret their own tangible, real-world experiences in their own words and minds. From there, these understandings are analyzed in the context of behavioral science, such as psychology, sociology, politics, education, health sciences, or, more recently, business and management, innovation, or decision-making, to name a few (Aspers & Corte, 2019; Cropley, 2019; Ritter et al., 2023).

A multiple case study involves analyzing several cases individually, allowing the researcher to examine each situation separately and compare them. By investigating various cases, the researcher can identify similarities and differences across them. A multiple-case design has the advantage of allowing for a broader discovery of theoretical evolution and research problems. To provide depth and comprehend a wide range of phenomena, it represents a variety of traits and extremes while preserving each case. (Brink, 2018; Diop & Liu, 2020; Ghazi-Saidi et al., 2020).

To pick up the participants for this investigation purposeful sampling was employed. This study uses a purposive sampling design that explores the challenges, coping mechanisms. According to Patton (2014), purposeful sampling is adequate when choosing cases rich in information for in-depth analysis. He defined information-rich cases as those from which researchers can learn much about matters fundamental to the research's objectives, thus the term "purposeful sampling" (Staller, 2021; Taşçı & Titrek, 2019).

In this study, the researcher examined the experiences of the guidance counselors

and looked into the difficulties of different responses to or views of a specific event to learn more about the participants. The case study method was selected because it offered a comprehensive mode of inquiry, had a distinct design logic, data gathering strategies, and distinct approaches to data analysis. Visualizing and researching the experiences of guidance counselors in public schools made it the perfect tool for this research. A case study is most appropriate for how-and-why inquiries, including operational relationships that must be tracked over time (Massaro et al., 2019; Yin, 2018).

In this study, I employed in-depth interviews and note-taking, paying particular attention to specifics and the relevance of emotional content and revealing a wide range of participant experiences. Seidman (2006), in-depth phenomenologically based interviewing (PBI) is a technique of open-ended reflexive interviews intended to study complex issues in the field by looking at people's actual experiences and the significance they ascribed to those experiences. Open-ended questions are used in an iterative interviewing process to encourage participants to reconstruct experiences related to a specific topic of interest and reflect on the implications of those experiences. In-depth interviews gather detailed information on participants' sentiments, primary motives, knowledge, and thoughts about the studied subject (Sudirman & Masfufah, 2019; Tomko et al., 2021).

The guidance counselors of public high schools were the participants in this study. Public high schools in General Santos employed only five registered guidance counselors. Only four of the five guidance counselors became participants because one was very busy.

I undertook the following steps in the gathering of data: submitted the approval of a semi-structured interview guide and cover letters, visited the Department of Education office and talked with the head of the guidance department, and inquired about the names of the guidance counselors and their respective schools, Furthermore, letters of permission were disseminated to the following: Department of Education Schools Division Superintendent, to the four School heads of various public schools and the four participants.

Afterward, I conducted individual in-depth interviews with each participant. Using a multiple-case methodology, my role was to create an environment where trust was established quickly during interactions. The interview process was significant because it gave me a vivid picture of the importance of being a guidance counselor in a public school. I explored their duties, responsibilities, and the

requirements for becoming one. It requires excellent attunement from the guidance counselors themselves to handle the challenges the high school students face, setting aside the guidance counselors' struggles. There is no self-denial; their power, ability, and skills in balancing career demands with obligations are evident. Their substantial information and responses were enough to describe their dedication to their calling.

After the in-depth interview, I transcribed the data and, with the assistance of a professional analyst, formed insights based on the analysis and interpretation of the data. The first informant was 56 years old. Case 1 was coded Empowering Mentor. He has been a guidance counselor in a public high school for three years. He has received inspiration to help, serve, and bless the populace. The second informant was 39 years old. Case 2 was Hope Weaver. Hope Weaver finds inspiration and fulfillment in the public school system, where he feels valuable and considers his potential as a guidance counselor. Although he has experienced a positive and negative emotional state of attunement, it has not hindered him from performing his job, for he valued the lives of the youth. The third informant was a widow. She was about to retire. Case 3 was coded Pathfinder Guide. Being a counselor was a significant aid in managing the family's affairs, which was what made her an inspiration as a counselor. Her position, as a guidance counselor in a public high school enabled her to understand the importance of the position, to which she could relate to the suffering endured by some of the parents. However, the event had made her meek. She had the power and the ability to keep the situation under control. The fourth informant was a psychology graduate. Case 4 was coded Mindful Listener. She persisted and succeeded as a guidance counselor for two reasons: The first of which was the self-fulfillment it offered while offering guidance to the clients. She could see the benefits of the complete focus and respect shown to them and the economic benefits. The interview process was well-documented and audio-recorded. I assured each of the four informants of confidentiality and non-disclosure. As a result, the revelations from the four cases in the study were consistent.

Results and Discussion

The tables below describe the similarities and differences of the participants' views, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights in their Emotional Attunement as Guidance Counselors in Public High Schools. This study seeks to describe the emotional attunement experiences of guidance counselors in public high schools. The following research questions guided this study: (1) How do guidance counselors describe their emotional attunement as guidance counselors in public high schools? (2) What are the similarities and differences in their emotional attunement in the various cases of guidance counselors?

Table 1. *Similarities of the Views, Challenges, Coping Mechanisms, and Insights of Participants in their Emotional Attunement as Guidance Counselors*

<i>Similarities</i>	<i>Differences</i>
Views:	Views:
Offering Spiritual Counseling	Able to Listen to Others' Advice
People Oriented	Show Fair Treatment
Blessing Others	Concentration is Better
Taking Responsibility	
Negative Experiences are Present	
Challenges:	Challenges:
Feeling Drained	Experience the Same Scenario with Parent
Lack of Cooperation	Getting Irritated
Lack of Support	
Children's Lack of Tender Affection	
Coping Mechanisms	Coping Mechanisms
Having Me Time	Spreading Awareness
Engaging in Social Activities	Build Collaboration
Seeking Help from God	Reschedule Another Session
Handling a Matter Calmly	Learning to Accept Things
Insights:	Insights:
Be Surrounded by Postive People	Appreciatng the Work of Guidance Counselor
Dedication to the Profession is Necesssary	Looking for an Inspiration to Go On
	Following the Right Thing
	Improving More

The table presents how the key informants varied in their lived experiences about their Emotional Attunement. Indeed, the Emotional Attunement of guidance counselors was subjected to various functions and therapeutic sessions in school, as evidenced by their challenges, coping mechanisms, and realizations as guidance counselors.

With regards to the similarities of the participants' views as Guidance Counselors out of 9 key themes that emerged for this category, the common emergent themes for all key informants were Offering Spiritual Counseling and Taking Responsibility, which emerged from responses of the four participants. Being People Oriented emerged from the responses of EM1, PG3, ML4; Blessing Others emerged from the responses of EM1, HW2, ML4; and Negative Experiences are Present emerged from the responses of HW2 and SL4.

Concerning their challenges, four themes emerged from the responses of the key informants. Furthermore, the common emergent themes were Lack of Support emerged from the responses of HW2, PG3; Feeling Drained emerged from the responses of EM1, HW2, PG3; Lack of Cooperation emerged from the responses of EM1, HW2; and Children's Lack of Tender Attention emerged from the responses of EM1, HW2, PG3.

Four themes emerged from the Guidance Counselors' responses regarding coping mechanisms: Seeking Help from God emerged from the responses of HW2 and ML4; Engaging in Social Activities emerged from the responses of EM1, HW2, and PG3; Having "Me Time" emerged from the responses of all the participants; and Handling a Matter Calmly emerged from the responses of EM1 and ML4.

Lastly, in the category of their insights, two key themes emerged for this category. The key informants' common emergent themes were Dedication to the Profession is Necessary emerged from the responses of EM1, PG3, ML4, and Being Surrounded by Positive People emerged from EM1, HW2, and ML4 responses.

Regarding the differences in the participant's view as Guidance Counselor in Public High School. The theme Being Able to Listen to Other's Advice emerged from the response of EM1, while the Showing Fair Treatment response emerged from PG3. At the same time, the theme of Concentration Better emerged from ML4.

Despite the differences in the challenges, the theme Experiencing the same Scenario with Parents emerged from PG3 and Getting Irritated emerged from ML4. Several themes emerged in the differences in coping mechanisms Spreading Awareness emerged from EM1, Building Collaboration emerged from PG3, Rescheduling Another Session emerged from ML4, and Learning to Accept Things emerged from ML4.

Lastly, the differences in the participants' insights as Guidance Counselors in public high schools were: Appreciating the Work of Guidance Counselors from EM1; Looking for inspiration to Go on and Following the Right Thing emerged from PG3, and Improving More emerged from ML4.

Conclusion

The study on "I Know That You Know How I Feel: Emotional Attunement of Guidance Counselors in Public High Schools" highlights the importance of emotional attunement in guidance counselors' work. The study provides valuable insights into guidance counselors' views, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights. However, there is still much to be explored in this field, and future research can build on the findings of this study.

One area for future research could be exploring the impact of the emotional attunement of guidance counselors on student outcomes. The study found that guidance counselors who are emotionally attuned are better equipped to understand and support their students. However, it would be interesting to investigate if there is a correlation between emotional attunement and improved academic performance, better mental health outcomes, or increased student engagement.

Another area for future research could be examining the training and support needs of guidance counselors. The study highlights guidance counselors' challenges, such as feeling drained and lacking support. Further research could investigate the effectiveness of current training programs and support systems for guidance counselors and identify areas where improvements can be made.

Finally, future research could explore the role of technology in supporting emotional attunement. With the rise of virtual counseling and remote learning, it is essential to investigate how technology can support guidance counselors' emotional attunement. This research could investigate the effectiveness of virtual training programs, online support systems, and other technological tools in developing emotional attunement and supporting the work of guidance counselors.

In conclusion, the role of guidance counselors in public schools must be considered in today's society, especially where behavioral and emotional disorders are everyday experiences of the youth. Schools should be ready to assist in meeting the needs of the hour. The focus of emotional attunement is critical in better understanding and supporting students in their academic and personal lives. This study provides valuable insights into the views, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of guidance counselors in public schools. These insights have important implications for practice, including offering spiritual counseling, being people-oriented, showing fair treatment, and dedicating oneself to the profession.

Future research in this area should focus on the development and implementation of specific training programs for guidance counselors to improve their emotional attunement skills. Additionally, research can be conducted to examine the effectiveness of these programs in enhancing the quality of guidance counseling services provided to students. Technological tools, like virtual reality, can be explored to simulate real-life scenarios and situations that demand empathy and emotional attunement.

In summary, the findings of this study highlight the importance of guidance counselors in public high schools and their role in supporting their students' academic and personal development. The development and implementation of emotional attunement training programs for guidance counselors have the potential to enhance their skills and improve the quality of counseling services provided to students.

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